

2007-2603/001-001

OIKODOMOS

a virtual campus to promote the study of dwelling in contemporary Europe

WORKPACKAGE PR EA 2

Implementation of learning programme: housing design studios

Authors: Johan Verbeke, Jao Smet

Collaborators: Jan Tucny, Viera Joklova

22/02/2010

Lifelong Learning Programme

This publication reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

	Life-long learning program : Erasmus Virtual Campuses 134370-LLP-1-2007-1-ES-ERASMUS-EVC OIKODOMOS
work package	Implementation of learning programme: housing design studios
PR EA 2	
authors	Johan Verbeke, Jao Smet
date	February 22, 2010

This is a report of the activities carried out during the implementation of the learning programme: the housing design studios related to the workshops which were held at Ghent, Grenoble and Bratislava.

1. INITIAL CONCEPT OF THE WORKSHOP PROGRAM	3
2. WORKSHOPS.....	3
3. FEEDBACK FROM WORKSHOP: ISSUES AND WAYS FORWARD	15
4. IMPROVEMENTS FROM ONE WORKSHOP TO THE NEXT ONE	18
5. IN CONCLUSION	20

1) Initial concept of the workshop program

The housing design workshops within the OIKODOMOS project must be seen in the wider context of the development of the joint curricula and not as individual activities. The time before and after these workshops was intended to test possible exercises, assignments and collaborations regarding housing development in between the partners involved.

By planning each workshop at a different time during the semesters different timeframes for preparation, analysis and feed-back could be tested and explored.

The pilot project between Bratislava and Grenoble (see report PR EA2 "Experience from Pilot Studio Grenoble-Bratislava") was used to explore the possibilities of digital media and the ability to communicate with each other at a distance discussing a joint project site, Dubravka Big Camp, which was later used again during the final Bratislava workshop as a common site for all four partners.

The first workshop with all partners involved was Ghent ("Lifelong dwelling – one side of sustainability"), followed by the second one in Grenoble ("Housing for diversity") and the third one in Bratislava entitled "Effective Housing". The Final workshop in Barcelona presented the work achieved and discussed with external critics.

During the project period, whilst developing the curriculum, the status of the workshop became more clear to all schools involved. It finally acted more as a trigger and stimulation point than just as an individual activity. To be able to define tasks before and after the programmed workshop, partners and teaching staff involved conceptually began to see it as a learning activity besides others. This (specific) learning activity contains different tasks which can coincide and can have been prepared before the workshop or, results from the tasks during the workshop can be taken back as a start for a new learning task or be developed further or redirected afterwards.

This understanding became a very important shift in the concept of what collaboration online and at a distance could be. It made it more simple to collaborate at small tasks without having to dedicate a complete design studio during one semester to it, collectively followed. Every partner with different levels of involvement and time dedicated to the project could easily join in, exchange information and have students participating in the joint learning activities.

As can be seen from the detailed workshop descriptions, there was a shift from sharing content towards working with it. Developing content together by implementing smaller tasks, made us achieve more at educational level and case-based solutions than organizing a very large assignment (which was the case for the first workshop). During the preparation of the Bratislava workshop, in July 2009 in Brussels, because of the shifted goal and context, the process of finding tasks which generate learning activities became much easier.

The workshops formed a chain of interlocking learning experiences that focuses on the status quaestionis of housing in Europe, and probes into the development of housing concepts. Each workshop focused on one stage of the design process and was organized as think tank delving into the future of housing in Europe. The workshop formed a focal point for the on-going research into housing at the participating institutions. There was no specific local site given with the intention to keep all options and possibilities to develop ideas and concepts open.

2) Joint Workshops

1) Ghent Workshop "Lifelong dwelling: one side of sustainability (semester 1, academic year 2008-2009)

The aim of the first workshop was to formulate, from a European perspective, the characteristics of contemporary housing, attending to social demands, functional requirements, spatial qualities, construction methods, and urban models, among others. This survey, elaborated during the workshop, formed the basis for continued development during courses and seminars in the home institutions. The workshop ran from September 29th to October 3rd 2008 in Ghent at the Hogeschool voor Wetenschap & Kunst, School of Architecture Sint-Lucas, Ghent, Belgium.

The objective of lifelong dwelling is to design a built environment adapted to young and old, to the inhabitants in their youth and later on in their old age. The aim is to develop the architectural and urban conditions that support inhabitants throughout the different stages of their life. Lifelong architecture is supportive, not restrictive.

The first workshop in Ghent focused on developing housing (in new or existing structures, communal and individual housing) that is sustainable at different levels and degrees: Lifelong living as structural element for new housing for young people (affordable and accessible for all); redefinition and redesign of existing houses and housing blocks for young people, elderly and people requiring help.

These items have been developed in design studios that contribute to the conceptual thinking regarding housing in Europe. The theme of the workshop was introduced through lectures, visits of interesting sites, small design experiments, and graphical analysis of examples and through theoretical papers. The workshop was designed as a stand alone experience but emerged to a steppingstone towards a more comprehensive design project. A variety of topics were touched upon: housing modelling cities versus cities modelling housing; liquid lives and flexible housing; the spatial impact of an aging society; technological aspects of housing rehabilitation; ecological aspects of the reuse of existing structures; the development of new spatial organisations for new social structures; strategies for improving the quality of social housing; all this was organised in association with local architectural offices and the Flemish department for social housing VMSW (Vlaamse Maatschappij voor Huisvesting).

After the workshop the different partners used the digital platform to communicate and share common insights on the different topics.

2) Grenoble Workshop (semester 2 academic year 2008-2009)

This workshop was designed as a combination of conferences and teacher presentations plus a design studio on the site of the GIANT peninsula. It is an area of 350 ha located at the west of the old center of Grenoble that is going to be developed in a new Master plan in the coming years. In this way, the OIKODOMOS project connects with the reality of sustainable urban planning (and housing development strategies as part of it) showing the diversity of agents and requirements that interact in a project of this scale and complexity, and opening academic work to the participation of the administration, professionals, economical investors and citizens. The OIKODOMOS team viewed the workshop in Grenoble as an excellent opportunity for students to learn about the procedures for the development of an urban plan, in which design and housing is only one of the necessary steps.

Day 1 : Wednesday 22nd April 2009 - Introduction day

Morning - Workshop presentation

Welcome address by the head of IUG, prof. Gilles Novarina.

Introduction to the workshop by Jan Tucny and the local OIKODOMOS team Stéphane Sadoux and Jacques Lacoste. Presentation of the workshop timetable, assignments, tasks, general organization, available rooms, ICT tools¹.

Handing out of the guidelines for students groupwork.

Local site presentation

There were two conferences given by academics and local urban development stakeholders, centred in the Giant Site and its context. These conferences provided an introduction to the context of the site, and to the ambitions and potentialities of the city.

- J. Lacoste, J. Tucny (IUG) : Site basic data and specificities. Grenoble-Giant site and strategic context for the development project².
- G. Jourdan : Giant site or the metropolitan space and transportation (Lecture « Scientific Peninsula project into the Grenoble's urban area »).
- P. Olivas (G.U-GPEUS): Grenoble, a major scientific city in Europe and its urban strategies. The idea to promote Grenoble as one of the main scientific, university and technological poles in France (and Europe) is exposed by Grenoble University development consortium and the project « Opération Campus ».

Midday

¹ PowerPoint J. Tucny (see www.oikodomos.org/workspaces, Workshop Grenoble)

² A part of this information was uploaded on the workshop collaborative website (see www.oikodomos.org/workspaces, Workshop Grenoble)

Every day, between noon and 2p.m., the workshop schedule was reserved to social events, informal meetings, and common luncheons. Students and teachers accompanied by local students were invited to discover Grenoble city, IUG surroundings (Olympic village area, new housing development, regional shopping centre area...).

Study tour

Organised for OIKODOMOS students and teachers, in order to complete their « abstract » knowledge of the project area by a real contact with Grenoble city centre, border belt and the scientific peninsula (Bastille, Giant, Centre). A picnic on the Bastille cable-car summit station was an opportunity to discover on the informal context, the urban panorama and metropolitan spatial organization. Comments and guided tour by IUG students, and J.Tucny, J.Lacoste and M. Carreyre (IUG).

Afternoon – Student workshop preparatory exercises

Presentation of urban development scenarios by IUG students (PowerPoint presentation, discussion with participants).³ This exercise allowed students from the participating schools to share common strategic references and to coordinate their contributions to the collective groupwork main orientations.

Site perception by students. This exercise proposed an active confrontation between personal perception of the real site discovered during the study tour with urban and housing development concepts prepared in each partner university's local preparatory learning activities:

FASTU- Urban Design Concepts and Architectural Concepts.

SLUKAS- Presentation of Bachelor Design Studio “Intensity”- Site in Kortrijk, Belgium that shares several characteristics with the GIANT site. Presentation of urban plan by Stéphane Beel.

URL- Presentation of general reflections after exercises- Site_interpretation and Mapping_Concepts.

Student project teams constitution. Students composed 7 project groups systematically creating tandems between architects/planners from different schools. This principle was directly inspired by conclusions from the previous Ghent workshop where mixed teams turned out to be the most efficient and creative.

Groups were registered on the platform www.oikdomos.org/workspaces. Students were divided into 7 groups of 5-7 people from different universities. The “shadow students” from Barcelona (students that follow the workshop from Barcelona, commenting the proposals and working on-line from a distance) were also integrated in the groups.

Day 2 : Thursday 23rd April 2009 - Urban Issues

Morning - Lectures on Urban Issues (IUG)⁴

During the morning, three lectures took place dealing with different aspects of urban planning, social housing, residential diversity and urban sustainability.

Presentation by Jan Tucny : « Housing for diversity »

The lecture reminded students of the principal aspects of urban dimensions in a Housing project : relationship with the urban fabric, urbanization process, spatial poly-functionality. Housing as a part of global development strategy, links to density, movement systems, accessibility, social mixity, services, ...

The project dynamics were presented as part of a decision-making process, involving the identification and respect of regulations, economic and social constraints.

³ Scenarios “Rubik’s Cube “, “Science city”, “Eco-Peninsula without cars” (see website Workspaces /Grenoble)

⁴ See pdf summary on website <http://iug-grenoble.fr> (INTRANET, rubrique OIKODOMOS, Atelier Grenoble). See also: <http://iug.xtec.fr> or <http://www.oikdomos.org/workspaces/>

The presentation highlights some local aspects to take into account, specific landscape, climate-energy challenges, scientific city development strategies, options for feasibility.

Presentation by Stéphane Sadoux : « Regenerating the Greenwich Peninsula »

This presentation aimed at giving students a summary of the massive programme intended to regenerate the Greenwich Peninsula in London, drawing from a wide range of environmental, social, economic and design issues.

Since the site used as a basis for the Grenoble workshop is also a peninsula – although at a smaller scale – the approach used and the opportunities and constraints do bear some similarities.

Presentation by Jacques Lacoste : « Housing in France, Housing in Grenoble. Some aspects of Housing issues »

The presentation aimed to explain the context of housing in a city, analyzing the case of Grenoble, including history of urban development and the main objectives sustaining urban housing policies. From urban planning oriented to city extension to a redevelopment of inner-city, actors have to innovate for social mixity and diversity.

Professional partners' contributed to the workshop 5 in relation to decision-making aspects in development and housing projects:

Presentation by Deputy Mayor of Grenoble, M. Philippe de Longevialle : « Grenoble sustainable city »

City spatial context and strategic priorities for urban development and housing. This confrontation with policy-making strategies was a contribution to the multidisciplinary approach of the European dwelling introduced in the OIKODOMOS project learning priorities.

Presentation by Ms Geneviève Fioraso, Member of Parliament, Vice-Mayor in charge of scientific development (slides presented by her assistant) and CEA Executive Assistant to the Director Ms Adrienne Perves : « Strategic perspectives for the Scientific peninsula / Giant-Minatech development ».

These two presentations and following exchanges with participants gave the students the point of view of the city representatives and local stakeholders. Elective people and major land owners occupying the existing site expressed their demands, constraints and possible options for the Giant site development projects and place of housing components. Presentations showed some examples organizing similar scientific site space and functions (Boston, Harvard Campus, US Silicon Valley, C.Vasconi project, ...).

From the pedagogic point of view, this part of multidisciplinary contents focused on local urban challenges contextualizes learning tasks prepared in every partner school and also the definition of possible housing programme for each common project groupwork.

Afternoon Studio groupwork

The seven groups began working in several computer rooms booked for the occasion. Each participating student received his/her personal login to be able to connect via the IUG wi-fi network to the Internet and OIKODOMOS “workspaces” website. A dedicated computer room with 15 computers, Internet cable connection and printers were reserved for the OIKODOMOS workshop purposes. The communication between students seemed to function fairly well, and conversations and exchanges of opinion on Grenoble and the GIANT site happened spontaneously without many problems. The different points of approach to the workshop weren't an unsolvable conflict but a possibility to enrich discussions (students came from different universities, countries, academic backgrounds, subjects and had developed different preparatory works).

Groupwork activity was focused on the first synthesis by project teams of their approach of urban-housing concepts, site constraints or opportunities, integration of stakeholders' strategies and selected development scenarios.

⁵ See pdf summary or presentations on IUG website (<http://iug-grenoble.fr> , then go to INTRANET , rubrique OIKODOMOS, Atelier Grenoble). Other possible links : <http://iug.xtec.fr> and www.oikodomos.org/workspaces/

Supervision tool place by OIKODOMOS teachers (J. Smet, M.Malovany, H. Pifko, M.Vergès, J.Lacoste, S.Sadoux, J.Tucny). Participation of external professional tutor, Mr L. Gaillard, Architect-Urban Planner, Director of the Municipal Service of Urbanism.

Presentation by L. Gaillard on the existing links between Grenoble policy of “sustainable urban environment” and Giant located projects. Presentation of a Powerpoint on Grenoble city and metropolitan region with visual documents possible to use as a documentation basis or to integrate in studio housing projects.

Day 3 : Friday 24th April 2009- : Housing, Diversity, Energy

Morning

Lectures on Housing diversity energy

This cycle confronted students with two complementary visions of housing diversity and new energy and environmental challenges in urban development: one from the academic research point of view, and another presented by professionals and politicians as actors and supports of local projects.

Presentation by Henry Pifko (FASTU) : “Energy efficiency in housing design”

The conference dealt with sustainable housing, environmental technology, low-energy houses, passive houses, the application of clean energies in dwellings, ... Several analysis and examples of existing solutions applied for some relevant housing projects in Europe were proposed as reference and possible inspiration for students' projects.

Presentation by Pierre Kermen, Former deputy Mayor for City Planning and Environment. “Towards the sustainable European City – Grenoble, Climate and energy”⁶

The conference highlighted the specific situation of Grenoble in its constrained alpine environment and problems the city has to deal with new climate and energy challenges. Speaker presented main local initiatives and experimental projects illustrating some effects of new urban ecology local policies and regulations (Plan Climat, Master Plan Environmental Annexes, ...) on the urban organization and housing design. Students were asked to pay special attention in their projects on some important functions played in housing development by spatial organization of dwelling and public spaces, water management, green natural « cooling », solar energy, sustainable mobility, urban and natural landscape, ...

Presentation by Yannick Goetz, architect, Municipal service for Urban Development, City of Echirolles “Urban Planning and quality of environment- experimental project oriented approach”⁷.

Conferences related to the GIANT Site and Urban plans in Échirolles, as part of Grenoble Metropolitan area, which is a leading city in the HQE (Haute Qualité Environnementale –High Environmental Quality) certified social housing projects.

Afternoon Studio groupwork

Students were distributed in seven project groups developing their housing projects integrated in each of 3 selected urban development scenarios (Rubiks Cube (multi-factor Mixity), Science City, No car peninsula). OIKODOMOS teaching staff (IUG, ST LUKAS, FA-STU, and URL) with support of invited local professionals supervised the group works and provided help, information and advices.

Day 4 : Saturday 25th April – Architectural issues, Housing design

⁶ See pdf summary or Ppt presentations on IUG website (<http://iug-grenoble.fr> , then go to INTRANET , rubrique OIKODOMOS, Atelier Grenoble). Other possible links at <http://iug.xtec.fr>) or on <http://www.oikodomos.org/workspaces/>

⁷ Idem

Morning

Conceived as an important component of complementary modules of lectures, this session presented by teachers from schools of architecture proposed to students a return to the basics of design studios. Groups entering in the final phase of project formalization and their design options have to integrate a transition from the wide, context oriented synthesis to the object/area focused and adapted design.

Two lectures illustrated this orientation:

Presentation by Mireia Vergès (URL Barcelona), « The role of Housing Design in Sustainable Neighborhoods »⁸

The presentation explained some of the requirements and strategies to attain a sustainable habitat. The analysis of building impact and global resources in construction techniques, principles of dwelling morphology and diversification of housing typologies were presented as examples for quality design. A range of Eco-cities were analysed as illustration of sustainable housing communities.

Lecture by Marian Malovany (FASTU) "The site – Bratislava/Dubravka" presented the site for the next workshop in Bratislava and several examples of flexible dwellings and sustainable collective housing. A series of Slovak students' exercises on dwelling typologies prepared during FASTU local learning activities LLA showed links with the previous OIKODOMOS workshops.

Afternoon

Informal Studio Work outside of the IUG because University buildings were closed during the week-end. Groups uploaded in the OIKODOMOS workspace the first schemes and drawings reflecting their ideas.

Social event:

Visit of the exhibition about « dwelling » in the Dauphiné region in France. Reception in the evening in the Musée Dauphinois Grenoble.

Day 5 : Sunday 26th April - Weekend

OIKODOMOS team building: Despite rainy weather, part of OIKODOMOS teaching staff visited with workshop organizers the former Winter Olympic Games ski resort Chamrousse and discovered its transformation in a suburban leisure housing centre. A common meal in a mountain restaurant and a walking tour across the ski slopes was enjoyed by all participants.

French IUG students proposed to their classmates to visit Grenoble and its suburbia.

Virtual Campus applied functionalities

During the weekend (Saturday evening and Sunday) many of the students continued working together in hotels and/or connecting themselves on-line (for example with the shadow students of Barcelona). Professor Kris Scheerlinck, professor of Urban Planning in La Salle-URL, assisted them.

Day 6 : Monday 27th April - Studio work

Morning- Intensive Studio Work

Students' teams worked in dedicated classrooms and IUG video amphitheatre. They developed an overall urban proposal for the GIANT site, considering all the issues analyzed during the workshop week. They had to integrate residential structures in the site in accordance to the selected development scenario global orientation.

⁸ See pdf summary or Ppt presentations on IUG website (<http://iug-grenoble.fr> , then go to INTRANET , rubrique OIKODOMOS, Atelier Grenoble). Other possible links on <http://iug.xtec.fr> or on <http://www.oikodomos.org/workspaces/>

Groups were tutored by OIKODOMOS teaching staff representing all partner schools. IUG workshop organizers tried to answer students' demands for confrontation with extra-academic professionals and invited the Director of Grenoble city Service for Urban Development, M. Laurent Gaillard, to exchange with students and supervise their designs.

Afternoon – Super-Intensive Studio Work, Management meeting,

Student teams continued their projects and finalized their design components and presentations. Each group prepared one DIN A1 poster summarizing their global proposal and transmitted a file to organizers for printing by IUG and displaying in final project exhibition. Poster files were uploaded to the OIKODOMOS workspaces web and IUG website.

Evening - Social event

Dinner with IUG colleagues in the Grenoble historical city centre restaurant.

Day 7 : Tuesday 28th April – Final presentations

Morning – Project presentation

Final Presentation

Each of the seven groups made an oral explanation of their work in the IUG visio-amphitheater, presenting a power-point of their urban proposal. Besides students and OIKODOMOS staff, others were invited to participate and discuss the proposals, such as invited teachers, professional architects from Grenoble, and representatives of different organizations and elected people. Groups were given a limited time for their presentation, which was followed by a period of time for questions, comments and proposals. The dialogue and exchange of points of view was very positive.

The presentations proved a considerable effort and level of motivation from the students. Taking into account the great complexity of the given exercise (urban proposal in the GIANT site of 350 ha), the lack of time and quantity of available information, the results of this intense week were very positive. The urban proposals must not be viewed as a realistic approach to the development of the site but as a field for reflections, suggestions, ideas and knowledge.

Final presentations were uploaded on the Grenoble University TICE videosever and accessible by streaming from links in the virtual platform oikodomos.org/workshops. Then, student comments and teacher critics evaluations were introduced. Some posterior activities and tasks related to the workshop have been set. For example Jao Smet and Kris Sheerlinck have asked students to reflect about the results in a more conceptual way to extract systems of urban analysis and models of growth that can be extrapolated.

Lunchtime – Buffet / Posters exhibition

IUG students participating to the workshop, helped by some of their OIKODOMOS classmates, organized an open buffet with French regional specialities. This buffet sponsored by Grenoble University contributed to the strategy of cross-fertilization and exchanges between different OIKODOMOS target groups. After the Project presentation session, participants exchanged in an informal manner their comments, suggestions, questions about projects, education programmes, European housing, ... A lot of contacts and opportunities for future cooperation were developed at this moment.

A workshop project exhibition was organized in the hall of IUG allowing each of the seven groups to present one A1 poster that summarized their work. During the buffet lunchtime students and external guests shared their comments on displayed posters and workshop activities.

3) Bratislava Workshop (semester 1 academic year 2009-2010)

The Bratislava workshop did built on the experiences from the previous OIKODOMOS workshops in Ghent (Lifelong dwelling) and Grenoble (Housing for diversity). It focussed on the effective urban and housing development in the suburban part of Bratislava corresponding to: site specific context, connections to the broader city context, life styles and situations, constructions and materials, low energy and eco friendly design, appropriate density, public spaces and amenities. Moreover the site situated in the impressive natural environment supported the principles of garden city design and the diffusion of natural and residential structures.

The aim of the workshop was to develop conceptual proposals for the Bratislava site on the international and interdisciplinary platform and to look for general models of effective housing design on urban and architectural levels.

1. Preparatory activities

1.1 Specification of common learning activities

Preparatory activities for the final OIKODOMOS workshop started already in May 2009 (half a year before the actual activity) with the selection and specification of the design theme (Effective housing) and the design site. The site has been selected in close cooperation with local administration (Local Council Dúbravka), to achieve the involvement of local government, experts, practitioners and citizens. Localization and the size of the proposed locality was chosen to include the interests of all project partners with various scope of design, including spatial and urban planning at IUG Grenoble, architectural and urban studio design at FASTU Bratislava, architectural studio design and seminar at Sint-Lucas Ghent and housing seminar at URL Barcelona.

The third OIKODOMOS workshop in Bratislava and relevant learning activities during the last semester of the project life have been in several aspects specific and most complex. Partners were able to build on the previous experiences and evaluations of realized learning activities. The Workspaces environment for the online and offline activities connected to the workshop was enhanced and fully available. Preparation of common learning activities prior to the start of the semester proved to be inevitable for their successful application within the regular study curriculum of partners. Accelerated discussions of teaching staff resulted in the specification of general learning activities (LA) and task sequencing (Figure 1) and the definition of corresponding learning outcomes.

Figure 1: Scheme that illustrates the learning activities and task sequencing of activities by URL and FASTU team.

Specification of general learning activities for the semester from September to December (January) 2009 were:

- LA1 - Perception and data mining
- LA2 - Urban analyses
- LA3 - Urban concepts
- LA4 - Architectural analyses
- LA5 - Architectural concepts
- LA6 - Finalization and presentation

During the perception and data mining stage the Bratislava team prepared the site analyses and description of the development programme, which were available for distant partners through the Resources in the Workspaces environment. Students and staff from distant institutions were already in the preparatory stage able to discuss design issues and locality determinants via the videoconferencing and online presentation, provided by FASTU Bratislava. Simple (Skype audio/video transfer and Teamviewer for the shared presentations) and more complex technical tools (utilization of professional broadcasting provided by student scientific TV MC2 at STU Bratislava, which was streamed online to specified web link) were used for this.

Figure 2: Distant site presentation and online discussions to the design issues during preparatory stage, Bratislava – Grenoble – Barcelona.

1.2 Specification of the theme

“Effective housing” was the specific theme for the workshop. Effective housing design can be characterized by the creative design, which respects the principles of sustainable development in the special conditions of specific natural, cultural and social environment, reasonably utilizes natural sources, human knowledge and new technologies, with the main objective of creating optimal and attractive living environments. It is a permanent and open challenge, which becomes a leit-motiv for actual professional discussions and new creative projects. The main reason descends from the characteristics of apartment buildings as the witnesses of human lifetime and represents a fertile ground for experimentation in architectural and urban design. As the consequence effective housing creates the environment, which is humane to their users and society.

1.3 Site specification: Garden City – Dúbravka Big Camp

The selected site Big Camp, which is situated on the north-western outskirts of the Bratislava district Dúbravka is big not only by its size (more than 50 hectares), but at the same time by its historical background and by its spatial determinants. There are exceptional archaeological excavations of the Roman residential and bath building (*villa rustica*) from 3rd Century A.C., which has been found and is protected in the area as national cultural heritage. The favourable living conditions of the area have been proved here by the settlements of Celts, Romans, Germans and Slavs.

The site is formed by the hollow basin surrounded from three sides by the forests and the massive of the highest mountain in Bratislava – Devínska Kobyla (514m). It offers the panoramic views on the west suburb settlements of the city, Malé Karpaty massive and castle Pajštún. Due to its north-west orientation it is open to the prevailing winds. The main part of the area is framed by the idle agricultural land and gardens. On the west edge of the site is the former glass factory – „Technické sklo“, built in the 70- ties, which caused environmental pollution and induces a sharp visual contrast with the surroundings. Nowadays it is out of work and can be transformed into new functions.

Moreover, the site will be affected by the large developments in the neighbourhood, especially by Bory – Lamač Port and Centrop. These, already approved developments, will create a new attraction zone for this part of the city with shopping and working/ administrative areas together with dwellings and amenities. The design includes the traffic solution with the connection to Highway D2 and with the prolongation of a tram line from Saratovská Street (Dúbravka).

2 Workshop Bratislava

2.1 Executive board

Viera Joklová, Andrea Bacová, Ľubica Vitková, Marián Maľovaný, Henrich Pifko, Zuzana Tóthová, Peter Lovich, Ivor Mečiar (FASTU Bratislava).

2.2 Participants

URL Barcelona –	9 students/ 2 teachers;
Sint-Lucas Ghent –	6 students/ 3 teachers;
IUG Grenoble –	10 students/ 4 teachers;
FASTU Bratislava –	11 students/ 9 teachers.

2.3 Description

The Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava blossomed out for several days in October by the international working aura. The mix of English, Spanish, French, Flemish and Slovak languages was heard from classrooms and ateliers. Inspiring impulses from the selected site and theme were stimulating students to utilize them in creative ways and to transform them into their designs within formalized international groups. The design incentive of the urban and architectural development concept originated from the effective housing design in the garden city. Coincident expert lectures were held in the first workshop mornings to fix the students more in the problems of effective housing. First day of the workshop was dedicated to site visit and acquaintance of participants. Design works within international students groups began on second afternoon. Students were able to concentrate on common work in groups, to allocate the work and to discuss the best

solutions. They were helped not only by local and foreign participating teachers, but as well by the external professional architects, specialized on housing design. The results of 7 workshop groups were presented and commented during the final presentation with the participation of the delegate of Local Council of Dúbravka. The presentations were scanned by the student TV and streamed online through the web link to „shadow“ participants of the workshop – the students from partners institutions, which stayed at home. The suggestions for the development of the area varied from the vacant build-up area in the mass of greenery to concentrated compact block structures. Inspirational were the solutions for the re-adjustment of the former Glass factory to the new exhibition and leisure centre, location of the new railway station for public traffic in the area and the accessing of archeological excavation within the established archeological park. The common strategic development scenario was characterized by the autonomous housing and living district with low storeys residential houses in a lot of greenery and the minimalization of car traffic. Final posters were published at the exhibition in the entrance hall of the Faculty of Architecture and will be re-installed in the courthouse in Dúbravka. Citizens, local administration, elected members and professionals were able to formulate their opinions to the students designs. The results of the students works will be considered in the future urban study for the area, which is prepared by the Local council Dúbravka.

2.4 Programme of the workshop in detail

First day Wednesday 14th October

Welcome of the participants by prof. Dr. Ľubica Vítková, Vice-dean of FASTU Bratislava and the organization team of the workshop. The planned walking city tour had to be canceled due to heavy cold and windy weather. Hence, participants started earlier for the site survey of the locality Big Camp in Dúbravka and Dúbravka surroundings. They received the impression of the solved locality and existing housing structures. After the survey they were all invited to a joint lunch to facilitate the socialization process between students. Later on the programme proceeded with the welcome by the Dúbravka Mayor Mr. Ján Sandtner and the Local council members and with the presentation of the development determinants of the district, social and housing strategies. The event was recorded and transmitted by the Dúbravka television and it was as well published in local journal „Dúbravsky spravodaj“ under the headings: „Will international students solve the problem of Dúbravka development area?“.

Students from participating institutions prepared and presented their visions for the development scenarios of the area. Students from each of the four institutions participating in the workshop presented a summary of the work done at their school during the preparatory phase. In order to make these presentations, the group had first to discuss the collective work done at their school, in order to pick up the most important ideas and to present them in a concise and effective manner to the workshop participants.

Figure 3: Welcome of the workshop participants by the Mayor of Dúbravka in the Dúbravka Local council.

Second day: Thursday 15th October

Thursday morning was dedicated to four lectures related to the issue of effective housing design, all of them were held by professors from the Faculty of Architecture, STU in Bratislava. The introductory lecture, held by B. Kováč, introduced students in the history, spatial, social and urban „Determinants of the Bratislava development“. V. Joklová and A. Bacová represented their view on the general „Principles of effective housing design“. Ľ. Vítková introduced the essentials for „Urban effectiveness“ of design. The chain of lectures was closed by the presentation of specific „Housing development in Slovakia“ by M. Maľovaný.

After a joint lunch with all participants the group activities started in the afternoon. 36 students were divided into 7 mixed international groups with 5, respectively 6 participants. Each group had appointed its tutor from the host university, who helped to guide the work in creative and logistic issues. Students were introduced to the details of the workshop task of "Site Development Concepts". They started their common design work.

The goal of the Learning Activity "Site Development Concepts" was to develop a concept for a satellite area supporting the idea of self-sufficient residence, with mixed functions of living, amenities, working, sports and free time activities. The final design had to consider:

- The concepts were framed in the idea of the central theme of the learning activity; effective housing.
- The following architectural and urban issues were considered: sustainable design, low energy design and design for socially subordinated groups of people (youngsters, elderly, sick and/or disabled people, low income).
- Green spaces should play an active role in each area with a functional, cultural and environmental use. In this context it was recommended to design parks, (green)squares, pedestrian routes and avenues in logical sequences, interconnected by the protected forests around the locality, so that they created an inner „green skeleton“ which could be used by all inhabitants.
- Basic transport networks, which link the public transport, to the existing superior traffic system. The transport development concept could count with the extension of an existing tram line. The use of existing train route as a secondary traffic system was desirable.
- The residence areas up to 1/2 or 2/3 of the whole area (ca. 33 ha). The recommended height of residential houses was up to 5 floors with private front gardens and semi-private courtyards. In selected areas individual family houses were suitable. Their design should fulfill the requirements of effective housing–rational (referring to the "effective housing; what's in a name" –task) with a proposed density of ca. 210 -250 inhabitants per ha. Floor space index (total realized floor surface area in the relation to the ground surface area) should be between 1,5 –2. It was recommended to design ca. 2.300 housing units for approximately. 7.000 inhabitants in this area.
- Local center of the urban satellite, which would serve the people living here. The center should offer cultural and shopping functions, services and offices as well as the basic health care facilities. The scope and the specification of these functions were to be designed in relation to the amount of inhabitants and functions in the developments in the vicinity.
- Reinforcing of the existing natural setting, which provides good conditions for the development of recreational, leisure, relaxation and sport functions.
- Reinforcing the area of the "Villa Rustica" excavation.
- Revitalizing the area of the former glass factory.

Third day: Friday 16th October

Friday morning five short lectures took place. The Bratislava City architect prof. Š. Šlachta introduced the „Actual issues in Bratislava city planning“. Following lectures were held by professors from Faculty of Architecture, STU in Bratislava. J. Ratimorská presented the important historical background and archaeological excavation of "Villa Rustica" footprint in the locality and surrounding area. R. Špaček explained the reflections of the "Ecology of the city in the sustainable design". Z. Gladičová presented the work participated at the Schindler award, in Vienna 2008, where she proposed the flexible and „Adaptable housing design" on the urban and architectural levels. Lectures were finished by the principles of „Energy efficiency" in housing design presented by H. Pifko.

In the afternoon students continued with their design groupwork supervised by the tutors. In the evening a committee composed of the tutors and teachers from foreign partners and with the participation of external architects from practice (P. Mrázek, Ľ. Boháč, Ľ. Závodný) viewed and commented the progress in design works.

Fourth day: Saturday 17th October

Saturday was devoted to the socializing process of the participants and to visiting the most outstanding new examples of residential architecture in Bratislava. The host university prepared for

the participants a guided bus excursion with professional interpretations about modern housing architecture, including the visit to the exhibition of modern art in Bratislava Čunovo on the peninsula of the Danube river dam and finally with the demonstration of traditions of vineyards in the region. It was finished by the wines and specialties tasting in an old wine cellar in the small town of Modra.

Figure 4: Site visit on the first day.

Figure 5: In Vino Modra.

Fifth day: Sunday 18th October

Sixth day: Monday 19th October

Both days were filled by groupwork in design studios with the supervision of teachers and tutors.

Seventh day: Tuesday 20th October

Participants prepared the exhibition of final posters in the vestibule of the Faculty of Architecture STU in Bratislava. The public vernissage took place shortly after the final presentations. The results of 7 workshop groups were presented and commented during the final presentation with the participation of the delegate of the Local Council of Dubravka. Evaluating teachers were provided by the agreed list of learning outcomes for the workshop learning activities. The presentations were recorded by the student TV and streamed online through the web link to “shadow” participants of the workshop. Re-installation of the exhibition will be held in the Local Council of Dubravka to afford the citizens, experts and elected members to express their comments.

3) Feedback from workshops

This section attempts at addressing the issues raised by students with regards to the content and to the organisation of the Grenoble workshop. These issues and suggested ways forward are summarised in the document provided by Paul Riddy. They are reproduced below and are used as a basis for a short response by the organisers.

👉 Issue raised:

More than half of the students who gave feedback made reference to the balance and content of presentations and of these almost half directly mention wanting less presentations and a similar message can be inferred from several others.

Comment from the workshop organisers:

This point raises one of the dilemmas stemming from the organisation of such a workshop. The theme of the workshop, namely “Housing for diversity”, calls in a wide range of social, economic, environmental and political issues. Tackling such a cross-disciplinary set of issues requires both methodology (programming, designing etc.) but also knowledge of the local, regional and national context. To a certain extent, this cross-disciplinary and multicultural dimension of the OIKODOMOS project is one of its main strengths.

It should also be pointed out that the length of the presentations held during the Grenoble workshop was a consequence of the need for simultaneous – or partial – translation from French to English for some institutional speakers. This occurs for example with Grenoble Deputy Mayor presentation and his dialogue with participants. This is a drawback, of course, but it seemed important to allow local decision-makers to give their point of view.

👉 Issue raised:

Exploring this theme further through responses not listed, three didn't appreciate the political element of some presentations and three others commented negatively on the balance of content, an example being "...clearly presented but without relation with the main work of the workshop, which was developed on urbanism projects".

Comment from the workshop organisers:

This comment is particularly interesting. It clearly highlights the fact that more attention should be paid to demonstrating the links between political decision-making and discourse to current architectural and design issues. The presentation by Stéphane Sadoux with regards to the regeneration of the Greenwich Peninsula attempted at drawing attention to the fact that the massive regeneration project which is still underway would not have been so successful if major political decisions had not been made over a decade ago.

It is therefore suggested that when speakers deal with the political dimension of a project, students should be encouraged to translate this agenda into a design framework or a programme to improve their understanding of the interaction between their own discipline – architecture – and the numerous external issues that dictate the context in which they will be practicing.

👉 Issue raised:

The role of communication in advance of the workshops

"The communication just started working when the students were here and we had time to discuss the problems personally working".

Comment from the workshop organisers:

This issue highlights the difficulties in defining effective distance collaboration processes between students.

It is suggested that videoconferencing – in other words, 'live interaction' – be strengthened in the future. This would allow students to get to know each other well before they meet for the workshops. These videoconferences could be introduced in the learning itinerary as « milestones » whereby a short report should be produced by the students following their virtual meeting. This way, a concrete learning outcome could be identified and assessed. Prior of the real workshop, contacts by videoconference have been experienced between FA-STU and IUG teams. If the live interaction worked well for video-sessions organized by teachers during local studios, other individual contacts or exchanges between student groups remain still too limited. Perhaps due to difficulty to share common, integrated or well identified channels and available tools.

Such a use of new technologies in teaching allows teachers and students to use the videos as a basis for improvement – both in terms of architectural and urban- design related content, but also as far as communication skills are concerned.

The footage also acts as an invaluable promotional material, which can be posted online and sent to relevant media as well as to the European Commission. It would in fact seem interesting to present this as an additional milestone in the project, to show that new ways of working are being designed throughout the project.

We also suggest that a short assessment of the presentations be made and a summary of guidelines be handed over to the students who will participate in the next workshop – in other words, ensuring that students learn from previous experience.

👉 *Issue raised:*

Similarly, a student pointed out that « By the way in the working space you don't recognise when someone is writing something to you. So you can't communicate / chat. ».

Comment from the workshop organisers:

The differences between synchronous and asynchronous communication tools should be made clearer for students. There seems to be a risk that asynchronous tools, such as the OIKODOMOS Workspaces, be considered by students as « live » communication.

Perhaps one possibility would be to introduce a chat room in the workspaces to allow students to communicate « live » without necessarily having to use an audio / voice tool such as Skype.

👉 *Issue raised:*

I wasn't sure about the work in Grenoble. I expected ?? But final project is OK.

Comment from the workshop organisers :

It is suggested that a standardised set of « student guidelines » be introduced prior to the workshop, so as to match the programme with concrete learning outcomes. The solution adopted in Grenoble, i.e. diffusion to all participants of a leaflet « Guidelines for students groupwork » with workshop timeline, aims, tasks and outcomes definition was perhaps not enough taken in account because of the quantity of new information and importance of getting to know to the Grenoble context. This Guideline was uploaded on the workspaces website before the workshop, but few students downloaded or consulted it. This information needs to be managed on the better way, with an organized support from teaching staff.

👉 *Issues raised :*

Students said they lacked time to carry out their project work properly.

Comment from the workshop organisers :

This raises two issues.

First, and perhaps most importantly, it appears that the concrete learning outcomes of workshops should be made clearer. This would allow students to understand what they are expected to learn and how they should go about carrying out they work. Time constraints will always be a problem for such workshops: therefore, it would perhaps make sense to identify a clearer set of tasks and learning outcomes so as to guide students in precise directions from the beginning.

Second, the issues raised also point to the logistical side of organising a workshop. The fact that university buildings in France close at 8pm is obviously a problem for students who want to work on their projects overnight or part of the evening.

Due to legal constraints, it would be impossible to open a building 24 hours a day unless consequential financial means were allocated to hiring security staff to man the premises.

However, the « Virtual Campus » principle permitted to some students to use different wi-fi hotspots in their hotels or in different Grenoble city public spaces and to work out of « normal » working hours. IUG students guided some of their classmates to these places.

4) Improvements from one Workshop to the next one

Some of the comments received after the workshop in Ghent helped to improve the implementation of the workshop in Grenoble (comments by M.Vergès URL, V. Joklova FA-STU).

1. Ghent:

Social interaction could be improved (maybe presenting working groups the weekend before the workshop and promoting previous social and touring activities).

Grenoble workshop:

The interaction between groups worked quite well. An improvised party took place one of the first days. Students from Barcelona and Ghent got along together very well, working together during weekends.

2. Ghent:

Teachers should have a clear common workshop program (with a clear definition of the activities to be developed) some time before the workshop.

Grenoble workshop:

The workshop program and the schedule were developed by IUG teachers, so this point was well-defined. In relation to the activities, there was a common idea to develop a design studio in the GIANT site, but it wasn't clear how- area to develop, work direction (more abstract or site-specific/ accent on urban dynamics or on housing), scale, goals and outcomes, ...

3. Ghent:

It is important to attain a clear brief and a non-ambiguous communication of activities and learning outcomes for the next workshop and courses. Students must understand the goals of the learning program.

Grenoble workshop:

In the beginning of the workshop the activities to develop weren't totally closed and defined (it isn't easy to impose a clear program of activities in an international program of this kind), so it was complicated to give one clear brief communicating the activities to be done and the learning outcomes to attain. In this case, the workshop had one main activity that consisted in a design studio project and this made that many of the initial doubts were solved along the way.

4. Ghent:

Enhance interactions between teams.

Grenoble workshop:

This point was OK. Another idea that worked well and could be further implemented was to include "shadow students" in the workshop. This idea was good to integrate in the workshop some of the students that weren't able to go to Grenoble.

5. Ghent:

Participants noticed the difficulty to include an urban dimension in the groupwork often dominated by the point of view of architects. But despite a little more complicated collaboration, a large majority agree on the interest of results presented by groups where urban planning students were involved. (Comment by UIG).

Grenoble workshop:

In this case, since the design studio consisted basically in the development of an urban proposal, there weren't these kinds of difficulties. Some of the participant universities, like LASALLE URL, include urban planning as a part of architectural studies, so they are relatively familiar to work with the urban scale. It was very interesting to put together the different ways of approaching the development of an urban proposal: IUG students tended to have a realistic approach, very conditioned by the real viability, considering always time factors and financial possibilities; Sint-Lucas and LASALLE students tended to introduce more abstract and radical proposals, which is also very positive and necessary at this stage of the urban development; FASTU students, that had already developed housing proposals in the site, had a very open

attitude and seemed to accept without problem working with the urban scale instead of continuing with housing proposals.

6. Ghent:

Some teams composed by a majority of Erasmus students seemed to be less efficient, due to the uneven motivation of participants, not really involved in the dynamic of study programme in host university. Teams with better balance of OIKODOMOS partners universities' students are preferred.

Grenoble workshop:

No problem in Grenoble workshop.

7. Ghent:

Practical issues- It would be positive to have a fixed working space (where students can work together when they want to), and also computer and printing access. Space to build models is also desirable. (Ghent workshop)

Grenoble workshop:

No problem, there were plenty of classes available, during Grenoble workshop. Excellent logistics in UIG: organization, conferences, printing, wonderful buffet...THANKYOU !!!

8. Ghent:

More teacher critics during the workshop. Guidelines for presentations. (Ghent workshop)

Grenoble workshop:

This aspect was improved in the Grenoble workshop.

9. Ghent:

Live final presentation with interaction and dialogue between students, other students, teachers and maybe invited teachers (Ghent workshop)

Grenoble workshop:

The final presentation was organized with time for comments, questions and discussions, which is very necessary to conclude workshops in an adequate way. Interventions from external critics were a new and very positive element.

The following issues raised after the workshop in Grenoble have been improved for the Bratislava workshop:

- Generally speaking, the workshop could be considered a positive learning experience with a quite intense working dynamic, in which students have been able to gain knowledge from a very wide range of areas (sustainable urban planning, economical, political and social agents that intervene in urban processes, technopoles, transportation tendencies, city regeneration, urban revitalization, housing, sustainable construction, ...). It has also been a very good occasion to develop varied abilities and competences (working in international groups, being able to explain and defend architectural and urban ideas, being able to achieve a common point of view and to communicate it properly, ...) Maybe the most complicated point is to integrate in a coherent and meaningful way this learning experience in the whole OIKODOMOS Program. It is very important to develop post-workshop exercises and activities that transform many of the inputs received during the workshops into deeper and re-usable knowledge.
- In future experiences, maybe the topic should be more clear and adequately integrated in the development of OIKODOMOS program in terms of content ("Housing for Diversity" wasn't really the guiding topic of the workshop, in fact housing was only one of many other urban issues presented). Many interesting topics have been arising during the OIKODOMOS experience, but maybe some kind of clearer program and goals (competences to be achieved by students, ...) could be developed.
- It is positive that conferences in workshops are closely related to the main topic of the workshop.
- A previous definition of pre-workshop, workshop, and post-workshop activities may help give a stronger sense of continuity to the OIKODOMOS program.

5) In conclusion

Although the partners only implemented three workshops (Ghent, Grenoble, Bratislava) they were able to realise a serious shift. Where in the beginning of the project the workshops were more or less a stand-alone activity (as is the case in most Intensive Programmes under SOCRATES), due to the intense collaboration as well as due to the support by the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus, the partners managed to change this perspective into workshops which are fully integrated in the semester's learning activities of the participating students. Moreover, the partners developed a flexible curriculum allowing interaction between partner universities and learning activities in which the workshop plays a focal point. The workshops and the supporting OIKODOMOS virtual campus helped and stimulated interaction between participating students, before during and after the workshop. The overall context helped to create an intense and enjoyable learning experience of participants, introducing them into the topic of housing and cultural and local aspects involved.